

“Human Rights and Citizenship Education” and in-service teacher training: an experience

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Resumo

O texto que se segue apresenta uma experiência formativa levada a cabo em três Acções de Formação Contínua de Professores sobre Educação para a Cidadania e para os Direitos do Homem. Essa experiência teve lugar dentro do contexto mais geral de um projecto de Educação para a Cidadania e para os Direitos do Homem que vem decorrendo desde 2002 e que envolve a nossa instituição – Escola Superior de Educação do Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra –, a Universidade de Granada e o Conselho da Europa (em particular, através do Centro Europeu da Juventude de Budapeste). Para este projecto, a formação contínua de Professores é uma componente importante, mediante a qual se busca um ensino e formação de qualidade e excelência. A utilização de metodologias de Educação Não-Formal é o traço distintivo desta experiência e do Projecto em que a mesma se integra.

Palavras-chave

Formação de professores, Educação para a cidadania e Direitos do Homem, Educação não-formal

Abstract

The text below presents a training experience on Human Rights and Citizenship Education which took place at three In-Service Teacher Training Courses. This experience occurred in the more general context of an ongoing Human Rights and Citizenship Education project, which has been overseen by our institution, the College of Education – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, University of Granada and the Council of Europe (in particular, the European Youth Centre Budapest). In-service teacher training is an important component of this project, which seeks excellence and high-quality in both teaching and training. The use of non-formal education methodologies is a distinctive feature of this experience and of the project it is a part of.

Key-words

Teacher training, Human Rights and citizenship education, Non-formal education

Prologue

This text aims at uncovering some aspects of the work we perform¹ at the Escola Superior de Educação of the Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, and, in particular, our experience of Human Rights and Citizenship Education at three In-Service Teacher² Training Courses. The need for Teacher Training in Citizenship Education derives from the fact that the Portuguese Basic Education Curriculum contains a transversal curricular component on Citizenship Education, as well as a curricular non-disciplinary component of Civic Education (Ramos, 2007; DGIDC, 2010a; 2010b; Afonso, 2007), thus corresponding to the great importance given by this Educational System to the students' personal and social development (Ramos, 2007; LBSE, 1986). Our institution already has a considerable experience in delivering Teacher Training in what concerns Value Education in general (Ramos, 2008; Reis; Ramos; Cunha, 2007).

This work takes place within the context of a Human Rights and Citizenship Education project, which we have been implementing since 2002 at the institution we are members of and at the University of Granada, through the Research Group DEDiCA. This project has several dimensions, which refer to research, training and community and social intervention in the area of Human Rights and Citizenship Education, amongst others. The activities involved include a series of diversified tasks covering all the aforementioned dimensions, of which in-service teacher training is an important aspect. Seeking excellence and high-quality in teaching and training is constantly pursued for this project. An essential characteristic of the project is the cooperation established with the Council of Europe, in particular with the European Youth Centre Budapest, to whose work we have linked the development of this project. The result of these vectors is the training experience presented here, in a descriptive and qualitative perspective. Our text aims at presenting the training experience in itself and demonstrating the evaluation carried out by the trainees, showing their own perception of personal and professional change and their judgement of the training performed, in particular, its usefulness for their teaching work.

The connection with the Council of Europe's Human Rights Programme is peculiar to this experience, making it unique. Therefore, it is not possible to refer it to other experiences. Nevertheless, Citizenship Education is a major concern of the Portuguese National Curriculum and we will refer to it in order to establish the need for such specific training of Teachers.

The text begins by presenting some basic philosophical and pedagogical theoretical notions and options supporting the definition of the programme. In line with Paulo Freire's educational thought, we think that education always presents a choice in political terms (Freire, 1974, 2003). Therefore, the first task in the presentation of an

assignment is the clarification of the basic axiological options of the author, in order to clarify his own statements and positions in what concerns his political and educational choices. Hereafter, we present the structure of the training courses and the results of the evaluation of the training performed by the trainees.

I

Human Rights and Citizenship Education, Citizenship³, Human Rights and Intercultural Education⁴

As stated above, education is never value-neutral, a condition that requires that one should assume, and explain what basic understanding of sense of education lies under a given essay or presentation. Thus, its presented political orientation may be stated and clarified. In the case of this article we are required to explain the following concepts that underlie the conceptual structure of the programme defined for the training: *Human Rights and Citizenship Education; Citizenship; Human Rights and Intercultural Education.*

Human Rights and Citizenship Education

The perspective of Human Rights and Citizenship Education presented in this article follows the Council of Europe's understanding of the concept. According to that official definition, Human Rights Education concerns «(...) educational programmes and activities that focus on promoting equality in human dignity, in conjunction with other programmes such as those promoting intercultural learning, participation and empowerment of minorities» (Brander; Keen; Lemineur, 2002: 17). This kind of education should allow people to become aware, on a daily basis, of the Dignity that defines the Human Being (Brander; Keen; Lemineur, 2002: 17-18), and this is a major task of education that has to be promoted at all levels (COE, 2010). It is, therefore, a major line of action for European Governments that translate this concern in their educational settings and legislation, such as in the case of Portugal (Eurydice, 2005).

Human Rights and Citizenship Education and the subsequent preparation of teachers to implement it are an important requirement in our time for a number of reasons.

Firstly, History has shown us a series of violations of Human Dignity, which require our ongoing intervention and commitment.

Secondly, a series of aspects have brought to the fore the need to assert and defend human beings as citizens entitled to inalienable rights:

1. Economic globalisation;

2. Technological progress;
3. Migrations;
4. AIDS pandemic in Africa;
5. Current challenges brought by multiculturalism;
6. The step taken backwards by Human Rights due to terrorism, ultraliberalism and capitalism.

Thirdly, the development of European Citizenship leads us to promote Citizenship and Human Rights taking the following into account:

1. The expansion of the European Union with the need to further democracy in countries that have recently come out of long dictatorships;
2. Immigration and the need to integrate the 2nd and 3rd generations of descendants in this process;
3. The need to expand the ability to participate in representative democracy;
4. The issue of whether the real seat of power in representative democracies is increasingly being held by financial and transnational organisations, thus pushing the role of the national State to one side and people's ability to exercise their power to decide their fate;
5. The need to socially integrate youth, a somewhat pressing problem depending on the countries and their demographics;
6. The need to solve the problem of chronic unemployment and of the structure of the economy of the ultraliberal and capitalist market.

From the conjunction of these factors – a non-exhaustive list, of course – emerges the necessity of caring for educational settings of such type of education, so that citizens are able to recognise the value of Human Dignity and its violations, as well as to promoting daily actions that make today's society more and more respectful of them, thus allowing Human Rights to become an essential component of everyday's life (Brander; Keen; Lemineur, 2002: 17:18).

Citizenship

Working in the field of Human Rights and Citizenship Education presupposes the definition of the concept of "citizenship", which is necessarily practical and political, in view of the axiological non-neutrality of education (Freire, 1974; 2003). In line with the

Council of Europe’s perspective, we follow the concept of citizenship in a *democratic* sense and connect it to a *lifelong learning perspective* (Birzea, 2000). This implies, firstly, that it chooses a specific view of what a *citizen* is, connecting this concept to the those elements of the European Culture and Civilisation that have lead to the emergence of Human Rights and Democracy but that are, concurrently, able to be universalised (Sen, 2003: 159-171; 237-255; Pereira, 2003: 7; Rocha, 1985: 84-86; Perez Tapias, 1996). Secondly, citizenship is a *lifelong learning process*, which is to say that everyone is involved in a process in which the achievements attained in a specific moment in life are not definitive and have to be constantly renewed and developed. This has two major educational and training implications. First, the Teachers themselves have to be constantly prepared for an ever changing reality and, therefore, are in a process of continuous learning, fact that we consider as a major presupposition of the training programme, as it will be referred later on. Secondly, being aware of the precarious nature of what was achieved is also a considerable feature of Human Rights and Democratic Citizenship because, as they are the result of Human struggle and praxis for a better society, they are also subject to disappearing and, therefore, needing to be protected and fought for in the citizens everyday’s actions, in which education is included as a relevant dimension.

If we analyse the concept of “citizenship”, with its Greek origins (Nogueira; Silva, 2001; Cabrera Rodrguez, 2002: 83-101), it shows us a constant presence of the idea of “exclusion”. Being a citizen is to be different from others that are excluded from citizenship, whether this differentiation is defined in terms of sex, nationality or income, for example. A citizen has always been defined by a differentiation from the *others*, who are deprived of the status of citizenship and its respective rights and obligations, and consequently seen as inferior in social and political terms. Throughout History, those who have been at some point excluded from participating in public affairs have struggled for gradual *inclusion* to access existing rights, or to gain new ones. A broader concept of “citizenship” should, therefore, strive for *inclusiveness* (Lister, 2008; Valadier, 1991: 82-103).

This outline implies that *tolerance* and *respect for differences* should be included in the concept of *citizenship*, acknowledging the fundamental reference to others - which humanity consists of - in its individual and collective elements. Consequently, *interculturality* will be another dimension of citizenship, excluding the concept of *identity* when it negates the essential differences that make us human and our relationships with others⁵.

Multiplicity is also at the core of this type of citizenship, since it is also exercised at various levels, for example private, local, national, supranational and cosmopolitan citizenship.

The outlined concept of citizenship must, ultimately, reaffirm people's individual and specific situations, i.e. their *personal* reality. This term simultaneously covers individuality and the fundamental reference to others or human intersubjectivity, which is irreconcilable with any generic notion. It is not by chance that this anthropological concept is essential in the philosophy and deontology of Human Rights (Rocha, 1985).

In short, *being a citizen* today is based on a concept of *citizenship* understood as *personal, inclusive, intercultural* and *multiple*.

Human Rights and Intercultural Education

The concept of *Citizenship* can only be consistent by means of reference to Human Rights, which constitute its core values (Birzea, 2000: 15; 26; 32; 34). They form the basis, which can become universal for all human beings, of a political and educational activity for the promotion of *Human Dignity*, as a fundamental and structural value of these rights.

In connection with the above, the issue of Human Rights' links with History and Western culture, and their limited applicability to other cultures and some other specific aspects of our hyper complex and differentiated societies⁶. The use of *axiological universalisation criteria* can categorise the debate and organise courses of action in the current world⁷.

Firstly, the absolute value of the *dignity of human beings* must be asserted. This is an *anthropological or personalist criterion*, whose *promotion* and *dignification* must be constantly reaffirmed and pursued. It is followed by the *dialogic or communicative criterion*, which presupposes dialogue and communication between social and political actors as a necessary condition to solve inevitable differences of opinion. It must be supplemented by use of an *argumentative or rational criterion*, which requires the use of a logical, dialectical and rhetorical line of argument to support a change of mind and the confrontation of perspectives that occurs in communication and dialogue. In order to complete the process, urgency and opportunity of action may lead to the necessity of making a decision, after applying the criteria defined above. The *democratic criterion* places the decision in the hands of the majority who makes a statement on the issue, whilst still respecting the rights of the minority or minorities.

Education plays an important role in the promotion of the ideals advocated hereby (CNE, 2000). By disseminating awareness, which makes it possible to unveil what does not yet exist, but should, it becomes possible to promote action and change. Consequently, Education tackles the great challenge of promoting the experience and learning *this* citizenship, through its initiatives and activities. This means that all its agents should

be aware of their ability to change the world, and that Citizenship, Human Rights and Interculturality subjects should take part in the training of all teachers, and not just of some "specialists" (Perotti, 1994). Training should make it possible to acquire the skills of understanding and empathy, as these are essential for educational situations. However, it should also provide a chance to reflect, and, consequently, to distance oneself from one's own cultural conditioning and respective inconsistencies.

Consequently, Intercultural Education must be understood on the basis of its two important dimensions, besides the mere *technological* dimension of being more of an educational resource that can be included in the training curricula of teachers (André, 2005). One lies in the potential to be a powerful medium to promote understanding between different societies and cultures and to establish the dialogue our times need, presupposing their equal dignity. Consequently, it has a *hermeneutic* role to play (André, 2005). This does not yet suffice, since there is an effective need to transform society. This *critical* or *political* point of view emphasises the fact that Education plays an important role in the transformation of society and, as a result, Intercultural Education is given a practical and political meaning since its considerable capacity to change society is recognised, above all by disseminating awareness to everyone involved in the educational process, or determined by it in some way (André, 2005; Freire, 1974; 2003).

Given this, intercultural issues are to be considered frequently in training activities, since in a globalised world no theme or question can be isolated in a specific context without considering its implications in global terms and in other societies. Human Rights' issues are particularly keen on this, and not only those related to emerging Human Rights (3rd generation of Human Rights), but also the civil, political, economical, cultural and social Human Rights (1st and 2nd generations of Human Rights) (Brander; Keen; Lemineur, 2002: 291-295). Also, the question of the universalisation of Human Rights has to be considered, as referred above. The specific conditions of the appearance of Human Rights in Europe, indispensable in their doctrine's definition (Rocha, 1985: 84-86), are not the same features that lead other societies to define their own predecessors of Human Rights (Rocha, 1985: 84-86) and this has to be faced when dealing Human Rights' activities in today's intercultural social and educational contexts (Pérez Tapias, 1996).

II

The training courses

Definition context

With the previous ideas in mind, we defined a training programme applicable to

several circumstances in which Teacher Training would be performed. Some variations may be considered, such as initial or complementary training, two processes that occur in the teaching preparation in Portugal. For this article, we have chosen to consider experience in terms of In-Service Training, involving teachers performing educational activities with the students similar to the ones they had received with their training.

As previously stated, there's a remarkable need for the preparation of Teachers to impart Citizenship Education due to the importance that this curricular element takes on in the Portuguese Basic Education Curriculum (Ramos, 2007; DGIDC, 2010a; 2010b; Afonso, 2007). The specific conditions of the country's History, bearing in mind its subjection to a long dictatorship and the implementation of a democratic regime, are on the basis of the importance given to the citizenship's issues in school curricula (Brederode-Santos, 2000: 53-62; 2004; Silva; Cibele, 2000; Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999; Ramos, 2007). In fact, this curricular element appears in the current curriculum as a major requirement for all curricula, since Citizenship Education is a transversal component, which means that all curricular subjects should focus on Citizenship. As well as a curricular non-disciplinary component, it also appears as *Civic Education*, thus corresponding to the great importance given by this Educational System to the students' personal and social development (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999; LBSE, 1986; CRSE, 1988: 119; Ramos, 2007). As shown in a study on students' perceptions on civic/citizenship education, «(...) there are intentional efforts, at the level of the planned curriculum, to promote the role of school learning in empowering youngsters for active citizenship in a democratic context» (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999: 500). Although this effort is translated into a carefully defined regulation and curricular orientations, as well as the production of teaching materials (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999: 500-501), it is not noticed in everyday's school practice by its agents who tend to perceive it as «(...) frequently episodic and discontinuous (...)» (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999: 501) in those curricular component experiences, despite some exceptions (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999: 501). This does not allow to «(...) ensure their potential for developing students' citizenship concepts, attitudes and competencies» (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999: 501), reason why this study points the existence of a wide consensus in what concerns the attribution of «(...) more space and time for teachers to speak and debate with the students (...)» (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999: 501). The analysis of the students opinions show «(...) the crucial significance of creating, within the school and beyond, spaces for interaction and dialogue in which citizenship issues, instead of being explained *to* the youngsters, would be discussed and analyzed *with* them in the spirit of cooperation and negotiation that characterises real democracy» (Menezes; Xavier; Cibele; Amaro; Campos, 1999: 501). This would lead us to the discussion – which we

will not develop as a matter of conciseness— of the necessary and potentially subversive nature of Citizenship Education for many of school and society dimensions, and its connection with the transformation of society that education should promote (Freire, 1974; 2003), as we can see in the discussion of Neil Postman and Charles Weingartner on this subject (Leighton, 2006; Clemitshaw, 2008). Nevertheless, it should be pointed out that social change may have effective outcomes through Citizenship Education, according to a study by Stephen Gorard, Beng Huat See and Robina Shaheen, in which less family support and social determination on the students' achievements is shown for this subject (Gorard; See; Shaheen, 2009: 35-45).

In this context, and in a similar manner of what is proposed for Intercultural Education (Perotti, 1994), every Teacher has to be prepared to conduct this practice, not only as the Teacher of a specific subject or equivalent curricular area, but also as someone who is able to focus the subjects on their Citizenship and Human Rights aspects and implications (Abrantes; Cibele; Simão, 2002; Pureza; Praia; Cibele; Henriques, 2001).

Although our course has been previously defined (2003) – in line with a considerable work on this field of teacher training performed by our institution since its foundation in 1987 (Reis; Ramos; Cunha, 2007; Ramos, 2008) –, it is worth looking at our training programme and its results according to an international study published in 2005. In this study on Young Portuguese Students' knowledge, conceptions and practices of Citizenship, the understanding of Civic Education/Citizenship it is also shown using the sample of participant Portuguese Teachers (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 157-188).

From the application of a Questionnaire, the study was able to reveal dimensions of the Teachers' perceptions on Civic Education/ Citizenship, namely the way in which it is implemented in schools and the opportunities that Students have to develop the knowledge, attitudes and competencies acquired both in and out of the classroom (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 159). The study's participants come from the educational levels from the 8th to the 11th year. The curricular reference and contents of the study correspond to the official definition of the Ministry of Education (DGIDC, 2010b). We will present the Teachers results and main conclusions to compare these with the results obtained with our trainees.

In general, the Teachers that have integrated the study had not been prepared to impart Civic Education and only a few had attended In-Service Training programmes on the subject (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 159-163).

Concerning their views on Civic Education/ Citizenship, the great majority thinks that it is important for the country, it contributes for the political and civic development

of Students, schools influence the development of the students' attitudes and opinions on citizenship, and school authorities give little importance to civic education and citizenship (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 165; 177). This is supported by a study carried out in England during 2007-2008 which shows «(..) that student/family background and institution-levels factors are relatively minor determinants of citizenship outcomes» (Gorard; See; Shaheen, 2009: 35), which means «that improvements here can come easier than in more traditional school outcomes, since they appear to be more sensitive to teacher and students experiences» (Gorard; See; Shaheen, 2009: 35).

In what concerns the curricular approach of the subject, the vast majority thinks that it should be a part of all subjects or of those related to Human and Social Sciences. Almost half of the 8th and 9th year Teachers reject the creation of a specific subject while 51, 9% of the 11th year are in favour. The majority of all Teachers refuses an extra-curricular area (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 165-166; 178).

Concerning the contents, the majority mentions the official curriculum, but a great number emphasises the negotiation of the issues with the students; it disagrees with the idea that what is important in Civic Education/ Citizenship might not be taught at school, and a very significant number also disagrees with the idea that the social conflicts and changes do not allow for the achievement of a consensus on the issues to teach (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 166; 178).

About the learning objectives and outcomes, we mention the fact that the majority particularly states how important is that the students learn to stand for their own opinions, to develop a sense of honesty, to become aware of the world's problems, to fight injustice, to accept and cope with conflicts, to recognise the right of minorities to express their culture, to participate in activities aiming at promoting Human Rights, helping people in the community and protecting the environment (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 166-168; 179-180).

Another element of the study explains how they see Civic Education/ Citizenship in school.

When asked about the focus of Civic Education/ Citizenship in school, they are invited to show their perception of the ideal and the real situation. The ideal focus of Civic Education/Citizenship should draw attention to these issues, in decreasing order of importance: 1) Knowledge about Society; 2) Students' critical and autonomous thinking; 3) Active participation in political and community activities; 4) Development of Values. The real situation's focus, according to the majority, on a diverse order, starting with the most important: 1) Knowledge of Society; 2) Development of Values; 3) Students' critical and autonomous thinking; 4) Active participation in political and community activities

(Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 168-169). This aspect of the study only concerns the 8th and 9th year Teachers, and it is not referred by the 11th year Teachers.

With regards to the actual learning of students at school, it is mostly emphasised what concerns the learning of how to work in group, to act in protection of the environment and to understand people with different ideas (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 169; 180).

About the sources of material and subjects used to prepare educational activities, the majority of the 8th and 9th year Teachers refer the media and the founding documents on Human Rights and Citizenship issues (Declaration of Human Rights and the Portuguese Constitution, for example). Nevertheless, over 60% refer the official curricular orientations and programmes on Civic Education as something not very clear since, by then, those documents had not yet been approved or distributed (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 169-170). The study does not refer this aspect in what concerns the 11th year teachers.

About the activities developed in the classroom, Teachers mostly refer the work with school manuals, the posing of questions by the teacher answered by the students, the use of task-sheets and the discussion of subjects proposed by the Teacher. Less frequent are role-playing, participating in activities in the community, projects involving collecting information outside the school and work group presentations. A curious result is the fact that role-playing and activities in the community are never used by 23% and 14% of the 8th and 9th year teachers and 22% and 13, 5% of the 11th year teachers, as well as the discussion of controversial issues is only frequent to 47% of the former and 35, 6% of the latter (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 170-171; 181). We are, therefore, in the presence of a teacher-centred teaching and learning perspective, and a considerable importance is given to manuals and task-sheets (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 181).

In order to improve the imparting conditions for Civic Education/Citizenship in the schools, the majority points out the time dedicated to the subject, the cooperation between the curricular subjects and with specialists. Materials and training centred in specific subjects are the less pointed (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 171).

In what concerns the evaluation of students, oral participation and written tasks are the most chosen, but 13% refer that no specific form of evaluation should be used; the daily socialising of the students and the observation of attitudes and behaviours is also referred by a small percentage (9, 8%) (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 171-172).

Another element of the study concerns the possible curricular contents for Civic Education/ Citizenship. The teachers were asked to choose from a list of topics which

they considered most important for the students, but also indicating if they considered themselves prepared to work on these issues, and if they thought the students had the opportunity of learning about these issues until they finished High-School, in this case, the 11th year. Firstly, it should be stated that there is a considerable difference between what the teachers think is important to be learned, and their own ability to deal with these issues, and then there is also a considerable difference between their ability to impart the issues and the opportunity for the students to learn about them. The themes referred by 8th and 9th year teachers are, in a decreasing order of importance, the environmental themes, the rights and duties of citizens, the civil and human rights, the cultural differences and minorities, and the equal opportunities for both men and women, while the 11th year teachers point out rights and duties of citizens, civil and human rights, environmental themes, cultural differences and minorities, civic qualities and equal opportunities for men and women. The item “Important events in the History of the Country” is ranked as the 8th (8th and 9th year teachers) and 9th (11th year teachers) most important, but it is the one that the Teachers think they are better prepared to teach. It is followed by “civil and human rights”, “rights and duties of citizens” and “cultural differences and minorities”, in what concerns the 8th and 9th year teachers, while 11th year teachers mention “environmental themes”, “civil and human rights” and “rights and duties of citizens”. As for the opportunities students have to learn about those issues, the 8th and 9th year teachers consider that the item “Important events in the History of the Country” is, by far, on the top, followed by the “environmental themes”. But when asked the 11th year teachers if they worked with the students on these themes, 75% said “no” and 4, 5% said “yes”, which shows the little opportunity of the students to study civic and citizenship issues. When asked about the issues approached during their classes, 11th year teachers referred the environmental themes in the first place, followed by the rights and duties of citizens and civil and human rights, mostly performed within the context of the subjects’ curricular programmes and of everyday school life (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 172-173; 181-183).

As for the students participation at school, teachers have positive perceptions, namely on the intervention in the Students Association and as Class Delegates. The organisation of cultural activities, cooperation with teachers in the solution of discipline problems, conflicts between students and school problems are also listed (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 174; 183-184).

Considering if the different school experiences the students may go through allow their empowerment, although referring that all of them have *some* or *much* importance, the spaces dedicated to debating with community members, with the class-director or teachers, the school newspaper and the school trips are more valued by the 8th and 9th year teachers. Nevertheless, only 33, 8% of these teachers, and 30, 6% of 11th year, consider

that their students are particularly committed in some project of intervention, which may contribute to their civic development. As to the 11th year teachers, they highlight the positive contribution of the work in the Students Association for the development of the self-decision capacity of the students, the ability to organise school trips, and to solve problems between students and teachers (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005: 174-175; 183-184).

Presentation of the training courses

With the aim of realising the philosophical and educational ideas stated above, our Human Rights and Citizenship Education Project implemented an educational and training course in three In-Service Teacher Training Courses, which were prepared and performed by the author of the present article.

An important dimension of In-Service Teacher Training is ensured by Teacher Training Centres, which are associations of schools established in order to perform this task. As well as similar ones aiming at enhancing their associated teachers' preparation, these associations also provide career management counselling. In our case, the training took place in a Centre, situated in a vast region on the North of Portugal. Each session was performed in one school year, and an associated school was the venue for the training. The idea of rotating the venue was ensuring that most of the associated teachers were able to attend a training session. Teachers need the training for two main purposes, that of acquiring more competencies for their teaching activity, and that of collecting elements for their CVs and to progress in their careers. The training sessions were scheduled for when the enrollment took place (by October/November of each school year) and lasted for seven weekly sessions, interrupted by school holidays and other school commitments, which meant that the training was usually resumed in February, and finished by May.

The main aim of these training initiatives was to disseminate Human Rights and Citizenship Education in the Council of Europe's perspective on this kind of education, due to our mutual cooperation. Together with this aim is the dissemination of *Compass. The Manual on Human Rights Education with Young People* (edited by the Council of Europe, in 2002, and which has been translated into many languages over the years⁸; Brander; Keen; Lemineur, 2002), and non-formal education methodologies.

In Table I we may find the total number of the Teacher Trainees that have attended the three courses, distributed by their level of teaching and gender.

Table I – Number and gender of teacher trainees

	Course 1	Course 2	Course 3	Total
Men	4	6	3	13
Women	18	7	14	39
Total	22	13	17	52

The teaching experience of the attendants ranged between two and 22 years in the profession. Participants of Course 1 are Primary and Secondary School Teachers – from the 1st to the 12th year –; participants of Courses 2 and 3 are Pre-School, Primary and Secondary School Teachers – 3-5 years and 1st to 12th year .

As in many other countries, the teaching profession is predominantly dominated by female professionals, as the table shows. The coincidental fact that course 2 registers a gender balance in numbers, which was not sought by the organising Training Centre, is notable

There was a large variety of teaching levels and years of experience. This diversity enabled very stimulating working groups, with very considerable and rich experiences of team building, communication and exchange of experiences. Some of the performed training activities addressed gender issues (such as domestic violence, for example), which usually raise very controversial ideas and opinions, especially in a country where there still is a number of considerable fatalities as a result of that social problem. It was possible to observe that the participants were able to face its different aspects in the most empathic, objective and effective manner, trying to analyse the phenomena and apply these to particular situations they knew, and improve their understanding. The diversity of the groups was mirrored in a set of members with extensive experience in terms of different teaching levels, and also with a considerable knowledge of diverse social environments and contexts. These conditions resulted in a remarkable effectiveness of the work performed, both in the training sessions and in the tasks assigned for the autonomous extra-session work.

The data presented in Table I is from the Training Courses registries, thus including all those that have attended and completed the course.

Objectives of the training courses

The Courses were defined to attain the following objectives:

1. To reflect on the importance of Human Rights and Citizenship Education in

contemporary World;

2. To relate Human Rights' issues with the personal and social development of the educational agents required by the Portuguese Educational Act (LBSE, 1986);

3. To develop the trainees' knowledge, skills and attitudes with regards to Human Rights and Citizenship Education concepts and activities;

4. To put various strategies and activities of non-formal education connected with Human Rights and Citizenship Education into practice;

5. To familiarise the participants with *Compass'* perspectives and activities.

Programme of the courses

The following work programme was defined to achieve the previous objectives:

1. Brief overview of Human Rights and Citizenship Education in Europe and its current challenges. Human Rights and Citizenship Education as a prominent concern of contemporary society;

2. Analysis of the skills and values of trainers committed to Human Rights and Citizenship Education;

3. Practical activities of group dynamics to promote and develop attitudes and skills connected with Human Rights and Citizenship Education and included in *Compass*.

Various practical activities to promote democratic values and Human Rights are implemented at the same time as the theoretical treatment of the programmed subjects. For example:

1. All equal – All different (on Racism and Xenophobia);

2. Ashique's Story (on Child Labour);

3. Different wages (on Discrimination at Work);

4. Do we have alternatives? (On Bullying);

5. Domestic affairs (On Domestic Violence);

6. Electioneering (On Representative Democracy);

7. Let every voice be heard (On Democracy at School);

8. Path to Equality-land (On Gender Equality).

The implemented activities addressed the following issues of contemporary society: democratic citizenship, globalisation, racism and discrimination, interculturality, child labour, youth aggression and bullying, domestic violence and violence in general. Based on these, the Trainees put together a portfolio on their themes, which included several materials susceptible of being used in future teaching of Citizenship and Human Rights (information, photographs, videos, etc).

The following results were obtained from the training:

1. Activities led by the trainees;
2. Portfolios written on the subjects of these activities;

3. Other products resulting from the implementation of the Human Rights and Citizenship Education activities.

Training instruments

The aim of the training, in line with the ongoing cooperation between the Escola Superior de Educação of the Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra and the Council of Europe, was to promote and disseminate *Compass*. Thus, it was the main training tool used for the training.

Other instruments were also used, such as an article on Citizenship Education written by the author of this article (Ramos, 2007), and a selection of texts for encouraging group discussions on the essence of education, democratic citizenship and Human Rights (Ramos, 2006).

Methodology

The courses were conducted under a basic methodological presupposition about the relevance of the Teacher's person for the pedagogical relationship. From the start we assume the relational and intersubjective essence of the pedagogical act, of which the Teachers' *person* is an important and decisive element, with the necessary implications in terms of his/her ethical and deontological development (Reis; Ramos, 2005; Ramos, 2008; Reis; Ramos; Cunha, 2007). In the methodological procedures adopted in the training, we aim at placing the trainees in a training situation similar to the pedagogical situation in its activities, contents and procedures. The idea is to make them go through similar experiences as the students when learning these issues. The similarity was achieved by doing the same activities when possible, and dealing with the same themes they might use when working with the students in future teaching situations.

Naturally, the level in which the themes were presented has to be adapted to the age and teaching level of the students. With that procedure, firstly it is possible to produce an empathic understanding of the students' experiences when dealing with these (adapted) issues and activities. Secondly, it is possible to use those personal experiences to raise a transformative conscience of the person of the teacher by allowing circumstances in which they are faced with the essence of value education, as well as of education as value conveyer, and reflect upon it. This personal transformation of the trainees' person may be of importance for future pedagogical practice on this subject's issues and on the teaching act in general.

The methodology used included several procedures, such as:

1. Group reading and discussion of texts;
2. Brief theoretical explanations;
3. Practical group activities, led above all by the teacher trainees, based on *significant, cooperative and participative learning*.

These activities are conducted on the premise that the *group* is the real *learning subject* and the systematic use of *group discussion* and *reflection* is promoted.

Beyond the face-to-face hours (25), the trainees have a further 25 non-classroom hours of written work and prepare materials and activities to apply in the training sessions and with their students.

III

Assessment and validation of the training courses

The Training Courses were assessed and validated by this group of teacher trainees using a Questionnaire, drawn up by the Institution coordinating the training in the region. It contained both open (5) and closed (9) questions (these were answerable in a 1 to 5 scale, "1" being the less positive value and "5" the most positive). The evaluation made by the trainees was completed by daily observation and registration performed by the Trainer, which goes in the same exact sense of the Trainees' evaluation results. The answers given to the five open questions were used to produce the main corpus of a content analysis, which is made in a qualitative perspective. The quantitative results are also joined to the analysis of this corpus. The biographical elements of the Questionnaire only included the Trainees' name, but it could be filled in anonymously, which was opted by 7 of them. Therefore, it is not possible to cross data according to the different variables of the population.

The open question No. 1 was answered in the beginning of the first training session and it was kept with the rest of the evaluation Questionnaire, in order to be accessible to the Trainee by the time the rest of the questions were answered, in the end of the training sessions.

A total of 3 trainees were not present at the final of the courses and did not fill in their evaluation Questionnaires. Therefore, there are 49 available evaluation Questionnaires.

The open questions addressed:

- Their training expectations (1. “I am attending this training session to find out about or master...”);
- How the training met their expectations (2. “To what extent did the training sessions meet my main expectations”);
- Training contents that can be used in their own teaching (3. “Some of the contents of the training sessions which you think you will use in your future work”);
- Possible obstacles to this use (4. “Some obstacles that may prevent you from putting the knowledge and skills acquired in the training sessions into practice”);
- Other comments (5. “Additional comments”).

The data obtained were processed by analysing the contents from a qualitative perspective (Vala, 2003). The validation objectives of the respective categories were defined afterwards, considering that the questionnaire had been written by another entity. This is the reason why the log units for a same objective and a same category could be taken from several questions, although the accuracy and requirements of the exhaustive and exclusive categories are respected for their internal validation at all times (Vala, 2003; Navarro; Díaz, 1999: 194; Van der Maren, 1996: 137).

The analysed assessments are subordinated to the following *objectives*:

1. To discover the teacher trainees' expectations of this training (Question 1).
2. To find out whether the training meets this group's expectations (Questions 2 and 5).
3. To find out whether these teachers will perceive a factor of personal, social and professional development in the training (Questions 2 and 5).

4. To find out whether this trainee group thought that the training given would be useful and applicable to their own teaching in the future (Questions 3, 4 and 2).

5. To identify obstacles perceived by the teacher trainees concerning whether the contents of the sessions could be applied in their own teaching (Questions 4 and 3).

These objectives will lead to the establishment of the corresponding *analysis categories*:

1. *Expectations*. The log units that fall under this category came from Question 1. It covers the Trainees assumptions prior to the Training start and shows their expectations on what would be delivered.

2. *Meeting expectations*. This category covers log units withdrawn from Questions 2 and 5. It intends to determine how the Trainees think their initial expectations were met by the training performed.

3. *Personal, social and professional development*. This category receives its log units from the answers to Questions 2 and 5 and it means to detach elements of perceived development of the trainee in consequence of the training performed.

4. *Relevance of the training / future application*. Category 4 received its log units from Questions 3, 4 and 2 and aimed at covering the perception of the Trainees about the usefulness of the training for their teaching activity.

5. *Obstacles and difficulties to apply contents*. Log Units for this category were obtained from Questions 4 and 3. It aims at getting the perception of the trainees about the main obstacles and difficulties they think are most likely to prevent them from applying their learning in the training.

Once the respective *log units* were detected, they were integrated into a data reduction matrix. The following aspects of the analysis can be highlighted. After each analysis, we will show tables with some of the pertinent log units obtained in correspondence with the category which is being referred (we keep the correspondent registration number of the data treatment performed).

Results of the evaluation

In a general and brief overview of the results, it is possible to say that the opinions collected show a great deal of satisfaction with the a) Type of training received; b) Subjects covered; c) Way in which these activities were implemented; d) Relevance of the training for the Trainees' teaching practice⁹.

Open questions of the Questionnaire

Category 1

The inherent analysis in category 1 (Expectations), provides reference elements that can encompass indications given by the log units of other categories. Consequently, it is adopted as the prior and necessary basis to understand the data provided by the teacher trainees in their assessments of the training. This analysis provides a series of expectations put forward by the participants in connection with:

1. The need to acquire knowledge, as well as materials on the specific training subjects (democratic citizenship, Human Rights and current issues, education in values, personal and social training, and educational strategies or activities);
2. To learn how to make groups, putting suitable techniques into practice fit for purpose;
3. Exchanging and discussing ideas/reflections/experiences;
4. Interest in receiving training (in specific subjects and in interpersonal relationship skills) which can be used in their daily teaching activities both in the classroom and in the community;
5. Personal enrichment;
6. Interest in career progression by acquiring the necessary accreditation.

In Table II, we can see some of the statements collected from those answers. What comes out of the assumption of these expectations and the needs revealed in them is coherent with what is shown by the study on the Portuguese Teachers' previously referred perceptions (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005), mainly concerning the lack of specific preparation for this curricular element and the belief in its potential for the students improvement and its consequence in society change.

Table II

Category 2 – Expectations

Log Units

- 2. “The best way of raising students’ awareness and respect for Human Rights and to lead them not only to act accordingly, but also to encourage others to do so. ‘Mustering’ information that will enable my own recognition and assessment of a democracy.”
- 4. “Rights and Duties of Citizens. To learn how to live in citizenship. Raising awareness and encouraging respect towards the liberty of ‘others’. Contemporary issues: Human Rights, Violence, Democracy.”
- 8. “Solving/discussing relevant ideas on certain issues related to the topic. Debating certain ideas regarding citizenship with the students, in the classroom.”
- 11. “Living harmoniously in society, observing Human Rights/Democratic Citizenship. Discussing and debating ideas. Issues related to the theme.”
- 28. “Choosing which strategies to use in the classroom in order to call upon and execute this issue. Motivational strategies designed to encourage students to live their ‘citizenship’. Strategies that will not only promote the students’ observance of citizenship’s rules, but also improve their respect towards the others.”

Category 2

The identification of expectations is followed by the analysis of the data included in category 2 (Meeting expectations). The records obtained indicate, as a result of the expressed views, that expectations were met. Some records even indicate that all expectations were met or even surpassed. The reasons given for this satisfaction are the organisation, coordination and dynamism of the Training and – especially important – the fact that the group was actively involved in the tasks. It is also possible to see the overall satisfaction as the training met their expectations and the consequent effort it required from them for those months of over-work and the awareness-raising for some of the issues addressed in the Training.

Table III

Category 2 – Meeting expectations

Log units

- 1. “(...) [it] exceeded my expectations, since the tutor was able to deliver very appealing sessions, resorting to participation and dialogue. (...)”
- 2. “I also appreciated the fact that recent events, as well as historical affairs, were included in the debates and related with the issues that were approached throughout the sessions.”
- 14. “The opportunity of applying issues to personal and social training. The promotion of collective thinking on citizenship and Human Rights.”
- 15. “I became aware of child labour, domestic abuse, youth violence and workplace discrimination.”
- 18. “It surpassed my expectations in every way.”

Category 3

As long as the subject of training does not merely become school contents to be conveyed and assessed at an objective level, and is taken as the transformation of the target learners and their praxis, we aim at analysing the perception of the latter aspect as revealed by the teacher trainees in category 3 (Personal, social and professional development), which to us is relatively more important than the others. The analysis of the data makes it possible to verify that these teachers have perceived a change in themselves, reflected on the three levels of development that were referred. Consequently, the following results are highlighted:

1. The acquisition of knowledge, with regards to the themes, contents and group dynamics;
2. Spreading awareness of and the change in attitude regarding values and preconceived ideas, as well as the capacity to act consistently;
3. Knowledge of oneself and others;
4. The development of capacities and skills (creativity, spontaneity, critical spirit, presentation, discussion of ideas/arguments, interpersonal relationships, application and practical implementation of education in values).

As we have seen in the previously referred study (Menezes; Afonso; Gião; Amaro, 2005), these results are also relevant according to the opinions they show, and they cover a wide range of requirements and necessities of Citizenship/Civic Education teaching and learning. We would like to particularly stress the fact that our trainees are aware of the importance of the teachers' *person* to perform this kind of education, and the development that has to be carried out in order to become possible.

Table IV

Category 3 – Personal, social and professional development

Log units

1. “(...) I developed skills not only related to Citizenship and Human Rights, but also improved my creativity, spontaneity and critical capacity.”
4. “These were clever, useful and up-to-date training sessions, where there was no room for dullness. We discussed relevant daily life issues, which we sometimes tend to disregard, in spite of their very real nature. This training forced us to think, to debate and to share our experiences on the discussed matter we discussed.”
6. “It proved to be a very relevant space for thinking and debating ideas. It raised our awareness for certain issues which are sometimes neglected.”
9. “(...) I developed basic skills which will be useful in my teaching activities.”
12. “It opened up new horizons for me in every field. It gave me a better knowledge of myself, with regards to my relationship with others. In the end, I had a different perspective on the way others accept me and collaborate with me. I realised that teachers are great for dealing with these issues in theory, but not necessarily in their daily lives.”
13. “The tutor was able to show the trainees all the prejudices that still influence [them].”
17. “It allowed me to develop skills on group dynamics.”
21. “It allowed us to develop skills on group dynamics.”
23. “Above all, I appreciated the fact that trainees had the opportunity to share their opinions and to be creative.”
26. “The training sessions observed human rights and democratic citizenship. That was the reason why I got so involved in my self-improvement.”

Category 4

This category (Relevance of training and future application) aimed at verifying the teachers' perception of the practical usefulness of the training for their teaching activities. Satisfaction with the training results is also pointed out. The perceived usefulness ranges from the fact that teachers are able to apply the contents, themes and activities implemented (tempered by adaptation to the specific circumstances of the course) to the group dynamics techniques learnt, especially in the perspective of their ability to promote values, personal and social development of the students, their critical spirit, sense of responsibility, interpersonal and intellectual skills and experiences sharing.

Table V

Category 4 – Relevance of training and future application

Log Units

1. "Methodology of group dynamics. Some of the topics proposed for the practical part of the training. Generally, I believe the issues discussed in these training sessions can be put into practice (if not elsewhere, then at least in the classroom)."
7. "All the topics that were suggested for group work were very useful. They were so relevant and real that they can provide group work and debates, as well as the sharing of experiences between students, therefore improving their democratic sensibility and also promoting the exchange of opinions."
10. "They can be a tool for the development of student skills. Improvement of critical thought, promotion of values and of a sense of responsibility. "
20. "Interpersonal and intellectual skills; Human Rights; Choosing the values that should act as guidelines for education."
27. "To use the discussed issues in order to discuss with the students in civic education classes (Portuguese School subject). Some of the provided teaching resources, as well as some of the strategies and activities to develop with the students, which I considered to be very interesting for practical work."
35. "The ground-breaking way of applying them to my students."

Category 5

Finally, we verified whether and to what extent the teachers perceived difficulties in transferring the training acquired to their practical activity. Consequently, category 5 (Obstacles and difficulties for applicability) has recorded the teacher trainees' perspectives. The log units are concordant with the data obtained in the previous category, and they are above all focused on aspects which are external to the presented training proposals and capable of being exceeded by the autonomy and imagination or creativity of the teachers and the institutions where they work. The following are especially to be noted:

1. Lack of resources, facilities and time;
2. Lack of understanding and support by superior authorities;
3. Scope of programmes and rigid curricula;
4. Organisation of school activities;
5. Resistant members of the Education Community, and of the community in general;
6. Preconceived views and ideas;
7. Students' lack of knowledge;
8. The impossibility of applying certain subjects or activities, in view of the specific

circumstances of some students or groups of students.

Table VI

Category 5 – Obstacles and difficulties for applicability

Log Units

1. "Scarce means and manifest lack of reasoning and support by decision-makers".
6. "The students' notorious lack of basic skills. Space-students relationship. The short duration of this kind of training."
7. "Too extensive curricula. Shortage of time."
8. "The resistance offered by other elements of the educational community and the community in general."
9. "Frames of mind, prejudices."

Close questions of the Questionnaire

The evaluation Questionnaire also contained, as stated above, nine closed questions, and briefly described in a quantitative analysis. It included a 1 to 5 scale, 1 being the lowest evaluation and 5 the highest. 49 trainees answered the Questionnaire, although the total number of trainees attending the courses was 52, as we previously stated. The questions and the mean that resulted from the answers may be seen in Table VII.

Table VII

Items	Mean (N=49)
1. Global satisfaction with the training course	4,3
2. Adequate contents and activities for the programme's objectives	4,7
3. Contribution of the activities developed to promote new learning	4,4
4. Development of the activities within the time foreseen in the programme	4,3
5. Motivation to move forward through autonomous work	4,6
6. The methodology used was adequate in practical terms	4,4
7. The methodology used was adequate in theoretical terms	4,5
8. The management of resources was adequate	4,4
9. The space was adequate	4,2

Although item No. 9 does not depend strictly on the Trainer's capacity and resources, it could be the subject to adaptations and changes. Therefore, we have also chosen to consider its result in this evaluation, which shows the trainees' satisfaction with the conditions offered for the training courses, although it is the lower value obtained in the process of evaluation. The remaining values are higher, and it is notable that all of them

are above the value 4 of the scale.

As stated above, the observation and registration made by the Trainer confirms evaluation corpus conclusion, both the qualitative and the quantitative.

The major difficulty with we had to deal with was the schedule of the Training sessions. There were seven sessions, six of which were four hours long and one five, always starting at 18:30. Usually, the trainees had been working all day long and some of them had to travel from the schools to the training centre. This might have influenced the psychological and physical conditions under which they would attend the sessions, but the training methodology was particularly motivating, and lead them to remarkable levels of dedication to the tasks they were asked to perform, along with their usual work with the students. The learner-centred perspective and participatory nature of the training are among the most important factors explaining the positive evaluation achieved by the training programme.

Epilogue

In conclusion, we would like to remember the descriptive and qualitative nature of this report, which only enables us to withdraw applicable results and not to transfer them to any other situations. What is valid for this group of Trainees is by no means transferable to others. Nevertheless, by presenting an experience and reflecting on its characteristics, we open the possibility of transferring the main conclusions and valid aspects to new training experiences and try them in other contexts and examples. Therefore, the conclusions drawn in this report are practice-oriented and have the scope of improving new and future sessions of the kind. We have been applying the results of the experience described here to other training situations, incorporating them in their programming in order to potentiate the effects on the trainees and what we have obtained here has been of good use.

We think that the evaluation performed by the Trainees allowed us to conclude about the usefulness of this training programme. It confirms that a teacher training which a) is performed in a learner-centred perspective; b) involves people's previous and daily experience, as well as calls to their participation and autonomy; c) appeals to their emotions, feelings, individual expression and commitment, as well as their personal interaction, may result in a very gratifying, useful and motivating process that the participants may recognise, cherish and respond with good-will and work. The use of non-formal education methodologies was particularly important to achieve this result in the experience, like in others we have performed.

This training enabled teachers to develop personal and social characteristics, which

are expected to help their development and that of their students. At the same time, the training gave them considerable satisfaction. These are desirable and necessary conditions to improve teachers' personal and professional fulfilment, by giving a small contribution to their perception of the value dimension of education and their role in the educative process.

The use of these same processes in the initial training of teachers is, in general, a possibility worth considering in formal educational contexts, given that they are also capable of producing the same effects in children and young people, a fact that has already been seen in other similar initiatives which we have organised, and which will be covered in other articles.

Due to the reasons we have endeavoured to explain in the preceding pages, we may declare that the results of the Training are very positive in what concerns the Trainees learning. There are, nevertheless, some critical points we would like to highlight to give a more complete vision on the range of the intervention performed with this training experience.

First of all, it should be referred that the training is but a start of an ideally much longer process to be accomplished with the Trainees. As a matter of fact, 25 hours are undoubtedly insufficient to produce a proficient competency of the Trainees in the subject of Human Rights and Citizenship Education methodologies, processes and contents. It becomes possible with this specific training to raise the trainees' awareness to the issues involved and to share with them some main features on this kind of education. There should be, therefore, a continuous training process with the same group, but the conditions faced by In-service Teacher Training in Portugal can be difficult at times.

Secondly, from our observation, we have identified some aspects in our trainees that must be dealt with in a second round of training, and to overcome, that is to say, the centring of the educative process around the teacher. In fact, our teachers are much used to teach in a traditional perspective that centres the educational act on the teacher and leaves little or no initiative to the student. This is absolutely inconvenient and useless in this kind of education.

Another aspect that has to be intervened on concerns the shortage of teachers' competencies and resources by systematically using group-dynamic techniques and activities. This should be the target of a second training intervention, as well as the conception, production and use of student-adapted pedagogical materials for Human Rights and Citizenship Education.

Nevertheless, to perform the improvement and follow-up initiatives previously pointed out, it is of decisive importance that the Teachers start by perceiving and

experiencing something different and that they have the opportunity of applying it in their training and practice.

Finally, we ought to mention that the continuity of such programmes depends on many factors, the most dangerous of them being the political ones, namely of a wild capitalist nature. As a matter of fact, the Portuguese policies of education have been submitted, for the last six years, to substantially unstable and contradictory processes that have resulted, amongst other relevant aspects, in a serious compromise and general harassment towards the Portuguese teaching class which, in its turn, has been submitted to a considerable work overload. Therefore, the results of the training experience reported in this article, prompt motivation, if we consider the potential of personal growth and group building.

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Notes

- 1 See Ramos (2005). The later implementation of this project from 2006 can be seen in Ramos (2009).
- 2 Hereinafter, the term “Teachers” will refer to primary and secondary education professionals, as well as early years’ teachers.
- 3 The following aspects are explained in Ramos (2010: 273-277; 2003).
- 4 Following the Council of Europe, we have opted for the term “intercultural” instead of “multicultural” (Perotti 1994). A synthesis of the criticism of multiculturalism can be found, for example, in Postman (2002: 30-34; 68-77) and in Valadier (1991: 82-103).
- 5 For the process of identity, see Daniel Sibony (Sibony 1997) and Paul Valadier (Valadier 1991, 82-103). The issue of “otherness” is given particular prominence and treatment in works by E. Levinas, G. Marcel, M. Nédoncelle, M. Baptista Pereira, and, in a diverse manner in connection with these authors, in the work by J.-P. Sartre. Good perspectives on the dialectics of identity and difference in a cultural level may be seen in T. T. Silva, S. Hall and K. Woodward (Silva; Hall, Woodward 2000) and in Amin Maalouf, through his concept of killer identities (Maalouf 1998).
- 6 With regards to the question of the universalisation of Human Rights, see B. S. Santos (Santos 1997) and how it fits in with issues of multiculturalism and globalisation. See J.-P. Changeux (Changeux 1999) for its relativism and criticism. A philosophical explanation of the intercultural question can be found in J. M. André (André 2005). It may also be seen the work of Amartya Sen (Sen 2003) and of Paul Valadier (Valadier 1991).
- 7 Trends of contemporary thought on this issue (Dialogical Thought, Personalism, Frankfurt School, P. Ricoeur, H.-G. Gadamer, E. Levinas, among others) are summarised here, using the terminology proposed by J. N. Vicente and J. V. Lourenço (Vicente; Lourenço 1993: 183).
- 8 In alphabetical order, we may find Compass in these languages: Albanian, Arabic, Armenian, Azerbaijani, Basque and Belarus (expected 2010), Bosnian, Bulgarian, Croatian, Czech, Dutch, English (original, 2002), French, Georgian, German (expected 2010), Greek,

Hungarian, Icelandic, Italian, Japanese, Latvian, Lithuanian (expected 2010), Macedonian, Montenegro (Serbian-Iekavian version) (expected 2010), Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Russian, Serbian, Slovak, Slovenian, Spanish, Turkish, Ukrainian and Urdu (expected 2010). *Compassito. Manual on human rights education for children* (Szelenyi; Brederode-Santos; Claeys; Fazah; Schneider 2009) was published for small Children, and is already available in these languages: Albanian, Dutch, English, Georgian, German, Hungarian, Japanese, Polish, Russian, and Turkish. It had its first edition in 2007 and the second in 2009.

Information on this issue is accessible (with downloadable material) at: <http://eycb.coe.int/compass/>

9 Other identical training activities, which we implemented later but aimed at different target groups, show similar results to those presented here. We hope to analyse the material obtained in their assessment and validation in future articles. The use of non-formal education strategies and activities in these training sessions in values, Intercultural Education and Human Rights and Citizenship Education, has proved relevant for other training courses that our team has performed, in which we detected change in the trainee teachers' attitudes; for the use of non-formal methodologies and meaningful learning, please see Gonçalves; Vaz; Ramos (2003); the change in the trainee teachers' attitudes by Intercultural Education training leads to the same results, which can be seen in Ramos; Vaz; Gonçalves (2003) and in Vaz; Gonçalves; Ramos (2003).

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